

DEBONDING DETECTION FOR CFRP STRUCTURES USING FIBER OPTIC DOPPLER SENSORS

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1 Introduction

Adhesively bonded joints between two plates are gradually increasing acceptance in safety critical applications such as automotive and aerospace structures. Therefore, there is a correspondingly growing need for the inspection of adhered joints in practical applications. Ultrasonic compression wave scanning of adhesive bondlines requires physical access to the joint region and is time-consuming and expensive. Lamb wave (a kind of guided waves) methods have considerable potential for the inspection of adhered assemblies for two reasons: they do not require direct access to the bond region, and they are much more amenable to rapid scanning than are compression wave techniques. Lamb wave can be excited in one plate of a bonded assembly, propagated across the joint region, and received in the second plate of the assembly. Inspection of the joint then would be based on the differences between the signals received on one side of the assembly compared to those transmitted on the other side.

A number of studies have been applied to inspection of adhered joints using ultrasonic reflection or transmission methods, in which ultrasonic inspection of the adhesive joints was carried out by exciting and receiving the Lamb waves outside of the joint area and judging joint quality from the wave velocity and attenuation in the different Lamb modes. Although Lamb waves have demonstrated great potential for structural damage detection, to date, the practical commercial exploitation of ultrasonic guided waves has been very limited. This is related to three major drawbacks associated with current Lamb wave-based damage detection techniques.

Firstly, Lamb wave-based monitoring strategies, often associated with complex data interpretation, are not appropriate for point-by-point field

measurements taken by modestly qualified nondestructive testing (NDT) technicians. Secondly, current signal processing and interpretation techniques used for damage detection utilize signal parameters requiring baseline measurements, i.e. data representing a 'no damage' condition. These parameters can change due to temperature or bad coupling between the transducer and the structure. Thirdly, a significant number of actuator/sensor transducers are required for monitoring of large structures. This is often not possible or acceptable, no matter how cheap the transducers are. Moreover, the physics of the interaction between Lamb waves and adhered structure is much more complicated, since mode conversion can happen between the region exterior to the joint area and the two adhesively jointed plates inside the joint.

The aim of this work was to inspect disbonds in lap splice joints of CFRP specimens, which was based on structural health monitoring (SHM) techniques using guided waves. Piezoelectric disc and fiber optic Doppler (FOD) sensors were bonded on surface of the specimens, functioning as actuator and sensors to generate and acquire guided ultrasonic waves, respectively. Mechanics analyses for the bonded assemblies were applied to optimally position the FOD sensors. A self-calibration transducer network was accordingly constructed and both the baseline measurement and the damage-related wave signals could be acquired at one excitation experiment, so as to minimize the influence caused by working condition changes of actuator, such as temperature and band coupling between the actuator and specimen after a long-term service. Moreover, arrival time, the simplest signal feature, of each guided wave signal was extracted and used for the purpose of disbond inspection, so as to promote progress of SHM techniques appropriate for modestly qualified NDT technicians in practical

applications. Therefore the first two above-mentioned impediments in SHM techniques could be depressed by using the proposed self-calibration sensor network and wave signal features.

2 Fiber Optic Doppler (FOD) Sensor

The FOD sensor is based on the Doppler effect of light wave transmission in optical fiber. Consider the light wave, with frequency f_0 , transmission in an optical fiber with refractive index n and length L . When an accident causes the length of the fiber to change from L to $L + dL$ in an infinitesimal time dt , the Doppler frequency shift Δf can be obtained by [4]

$$\Delta f = -\frac{n}{\lambda_0} \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where λ_0 is the light wavelength in the vacuum, and λ_0/n is the light wavelength in the media.

In the previous study [4], three kinds of FOD sensors with different shapes were proposed, named circular loop FOD sensor, U-shape sensor, and elongated circular loop FOD sensors, respectively. Common shape of these FOD sensors is the circular part, as sketched in Fig. 1(a). Points A and B denote the light source and observer, respectively. The theoretical Doppler frequency shift Δf of the circular loop FOD sensors is obtained by [12, 17]

$$\Delta f = -\frac{\pi R n_{eq}}{\lambda_0} (\dot{\epsilon}_x + \dot{\epsilon}_y) = -\frac{\pi D n_{eq}}{2 \lambda_0} (\dot{\epsilon}_x + \dot{\epsilon}_y) \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_x$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_y$ are the strain rates on x - and y -axes, respectively, R and D are radius and diameter of the circular part of the FOD sensor, respectively, n_{eq} is the equivalent refractive index of the waveguide and λ_0/n_{eq} is the equivalent length of light wave in the waveguide. If the effective sensing length of FOD sensor is defined as the total length in the sensing area (denoted by L), it is evident that the Doppler frequency shift Δf is directly proportional to effective sensing optical fiber length of the FOD sensor.

In practical applications, the FOD sensor is usually fabricated into spiral shape, so as to make it easy to be bonded on surface of structure or embedded in the structure. Moreover the spiral shape can elongate

the sensing optical fiber and therefore increase sensitivity of the FOD sensor. A spiral FOD sensor is schematically shown in Fig. 1(b). Fig. 1(c) depicts a surface-bonded spiral FOD sensor. Inner and outer diameters of the spiral FOD sensors applied in the present study are 8 mm and 21.2 mm, respectively.

Fig. 1. (a) The circular loop FOD sensor, (b) sketch of the spiral FOD sensor, and (c) picture of a surface-bonded spiral FOD sensor.

3 Experiments and Analyses

Sixteen plies of Tenax-112 carbon fiber prepreg (Toho Tenax co., Ltd., Japan) were stacked in accordance with $[0/90]_{4s}$ to fabricate the CFRP laminates. Dimensions of each CFRP plate are $L245 \times W25 \times TH2.27 \text{ mm}^3$. To fabricate the bonded specimen, firstly, two of the plates were joined by using epoxy Araldite[®] Adhesive 2011 (Huntsman International LLC.) and fastened with a clamp. Length and thickness of the joint region of the epoxy layer are 30 mm and 0.15 mm, respectively. Curing process comprises two steps: 1) curing at room temperature for 24 hours with the clamp; 2) post curing at

40 °C for 16 hours without the clamp. Disbonds were introduced by inserting thin Teflon® films in the lap splice joints.

3.1 Experimental System

In the previous studies [4], a novel optical fiber sensor, fiber optic Doppler (FOD) sensor, was proposed for the purpose of ultrasonic detection and damage identification. Spiral FOD sensors with inner diameter 8 mm and outer diameter 21.2 mm are used in this study [4]. In the experiments, PZT disc (diameter: 6.9 mm, thickness: 0.5 mm) served as actuator to generate guided wave in the specimens. NI PXI-6115 (National Instruments Co., USA) simultaneously functioned as incident wave generator and ultrasonic acquisition device. The PXI-6115-generated incident wave was amplified using Piezo Driver Amplifier M-2643 (MESS-TEK Co., Japan) and then emitted into the actuator. Semiconductor interferometer (Lazoc Inc., Japan) was used to convert the Doppler frequency shift of the FOD sensor into voltage, inputted into the NI PXI-6115 for signal acquisition. Hanning-windowed tone-burst with 5 sinusoidal cycles was applied as incident wave [5], amplified and emitted into the PZT actuator to excite guided waves. Central frequency of the tone-burst and the sampling frequency are 330 kHz and 4 MHz, respectively.

Fig. 2. Sketch of the specimen and zoom-in view of the lap splice joint.

To investigate characteristics of the lap splice joint in the CFRP structures, finite element analyses (FEA) were performed on MSC.Marc Mentat (MSC Software Corporation) software platform to simulate and complete elastic analysis for the specimens. Further, transducer network can also be optimized based on the simulation results for the purpose of damage assessment. In the simulation, extension forces were added at the two ends of the specimen, which are changed from 0 kgf (kilogram-force) to 640 kgf with the step of 80 kgf. To minimize torque effect to the lap splice joint, two tablets were added

at the both ends of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 2. Without losing generality, only part of the specimen, including the lap splice joint, was used to illustrate the simulation results, shown the x -axis in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3. Strain distribution of the epoxy side at the adhered boundary in (a) longitude, (b) peel and (c) shear directions.

Simulation results are shown in Fig. 3, in which strain distributions of the adhered boundary at the epoxy side were addressed in three directions, namely, longitude, peel and shear directions. According to the results, in the cases of all the three directions, maximum strain happens at the point A in Fig. 2 of the joint section. Moreover, strain at the right end of the joint section is also relatively

larger than that of the middle adhered section. These simulation results disclose that, in the case of lap splice joint in this study, the strain distributions in all directions at the joint section like a concave shape, implying that debonding damage usually firstly happens from the ends (A, B, C and D in the zoom-in view in Fig. 2) of the joint section. Therefore, in the specimen fabrication process, debonding damages were introduced by inserting thin Teflon® films in the lap splice joint. Debonding length was measured from point A, which are 0 mm (for the intact case), 5 mm, 10 mm, 15 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm in the experiments.

3.2 Elastic Analyses of the Assemblies

Much effort worldwide has been applied to the inspection of adhered joints using ultrasonic reflection or transmission methods [1, 2], which are usually based on the fact that Lamb waves can be excited in one plate (named exciting plate) of a bonded assembly, propagated across the joint region, and received in the second plate (named receiving plate) of the assembly. Therefore, inspection of the joint would be based on the differences between the signals received on one side of the assembly compared to those transmitted on the other side. However, Lamb wave propagation is much more complicated. Lamb waves (e.g. the fundamental symmetric, S_0 , and anti-symmetric, A_0 , wave modes) are excited on the plate outside the bonded region. When they reach the bonded region, they are converted to Lamb waves permissible in the plate region with a new value of thickness-frequency product, e.g. the S_1 and the A_1 waves [2, 6]. Moreover, this transformation will be different for a variety of contacts (slip or rigid) and materials [2]. Therefore, signal interpretation will become much more complicated for damage identification in the case of debonding inspection, which is also one of the most important afore-mentioned impediments of SHM techniques.

3.3 Self-calibration Sensor Network

In this study, a novel transducer network configuration, named self-calibration sensor network in this study, is proposed for debonding damage detection, by which both the baseline measurement and damage-related guided wave signals can be acquired at one excitation and therefore exciting conditions of the baseline and the damage-related signal are same in every inspection. For illustration, the proposed sensor configuration for the specimens is shown in Fig. 4. Two spiral FOD sensors were bonded on the opposite surfaces of the lap splice joint and named ‘*FOD-Front*’ and ‘*FOD-Back*’, respectively. Distance between the PZT actuator and two FOD sensors is 170 mm. In order to detect the artificial disbands in the specimens, guided ultrasonic wave signal captured by the *FOD-back* sensor serves as baseline

measurement to calibrate the wave signal captured by the *FOD-Front* sensor.

Fig. 4. Wave propagation in assembly with lap splice joint.

4 Guided Wave-Based Debonding Detection

As aforementioned, disbond usually happens from the left end of the lap splice joint in the specimens. Wave propagation in the bonded assembly in Fig. 4 [2] indicates that guided waves propagate through the adhesive joint and continuously propagate in the Plate-#2. When disbond happens from the ‘*Debonding Start*’ point of the adhesive joint, guided waves will arrive a little later than that in intact assembly. On the other hand, existence of disbond can only faintly influence the wave propagation in the Plate-#1 of the assembly and the effects can be ignored, implying that arrival time of the guided wave acquired by the *FOD-Back* sensor will keep invariable. Hence, the *FOD-Back*-based signal can be used as baseline to calibrate the *FOD-Front*-based signal, so as to investigate the integrity of the lap splice joint. Moreover, both the baseline (the *FOD-Back*-based signal) and the disbond-related signal (the *FOD-Front*-based signal) can be captured by just using one excitation, indicating that the aforementioned excitation-condition-caused drawbacks of conventional transducer networks can be overcome by using the self-calibration sensor network proposed in this study.

The previously proposed signal processing algorithm [4] based on FIR filter and Hilbert transform was used to simplify the features of the acquired guided wave signals and signal envelopes were consequently obtained. For illustration, envelopes of the *FOD-Front*- and *FOD-Back*-captured signals captured from the intact and 25mm-debonded assemblies are depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Envelopes of guided wave signals acquired by the FOD-Front and FOD-Back sensors bonded on (a) intact, and (b) 25mm-debonding assemblies

When disbond happens in the adhesive joint area, it is apprehensible that both the guided wave signals acquired by the *FOD-Front* and *FOD-Back* sensors will be affected. For illustration, the signal envelopes of the 25mm-debonding assembly are shown in Fig. 5(b). It is evident that signal components after 200 μs of the *FOD-Front*-based signal are greatly different from those of the *FOD-Back*-based signal. However, as already mentioned, complicated signal interpretation make it difficult to detect damage for NDT engineers. Therefore, much simpler signal features should be selected for damage detection in practical applications. By comparing results of the intact and 10mm-debonding assemblies in Figs. 4(a) and (b), it can be seen that the *FOD-Front*-acquired signal arrives a little later than the *FOD-Back*-acquired signal (the dash-dot-line circled area in Fig. 5(b)), which is because that the disbond postpones the transmission from Plate-#1 to Plate-#2 of the assembly at the joint area. Hence, the arrival time can be applied here to determine existence of disbond, which should be the simplest and most distinct signal feature for integrity assessment in guided wave-based damage identification. Moreover, arrival times of the *FOD-Back*-based signals for all the assemblies used in this study are same, indicating that the *FOD-Back*-captured signals can serve as the baseline to calibrate the arrival time of the *FOD-Front*-captured signals for disbond detection. Relation between the time delay and the debonding length and their linear fitting are shown in Fig. 5. The results demonstrate that the time delay is directly proportional to the debonding length in lap splice joint of the assemblies.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, structures with lap splice joint were conducted for the purpose of guided-wave-based debonding damage detection. Fiber optic Doppler (FOD) sensors were used to acquire guided ultrasonic waves

propagating in bonded structures, namely carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) bonded assemblies. To overcome the drawbacks of conventional structural health monitoring techniques, a self-calibration sensor network configuration was proposed based on elastic analyses of the structures in the present study. Both the baseline and the damage-related signals could therefore be measured in one excitation. Moreover, the most distinct and simplest signal feature, namely arrival time of the first wave package, was extracted and applied to identify disbonds in lap splice joint of the specimens. Disbonds postpone the arrival time of the debonding-related guided wave signals in comparison with the baseline measurements. The self-calibration sensor network is expected to be used for integrity assessment of structures with other damage forms.

Fig. 6. Relation and their linear fittings between the debonding length and the time delay.

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